

FORMULATION ABOUT TIME- AND TEMPERATURE-DEPENDENT FLEXURAL MODULUS OF DISCONTINUOUS CARBON FIBER MAT REINFORCED THERMOPLASTICS

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ABSTRACT

The ratio of in-plane elastic modulus and out-of-plane shear modulus (E_1/G_{13}) is known to affect flexural modulus when E_1/G_{13} becomes large and structure becomes small. And E_1/G_{13} of CFRP, in especially CFRTP, is also known to be very large compared to metallic materials. Hence, when CFRTP is applied to such as passenger automobile, it becomes important to know the influence of both temperature and strain rate on G_{13} .

As a result of this paper, it was quantitatively clarified that the time- and temperature-dependence of flexural modulus of CMT is caused by viscoelastic property of matrix resin. These results indicate that the time- and temperature-dependence of flexural modulus of CMT were able to be predicted by Young's modulus and by out-of-plane shear modulus influenced from viscoelastic property of matrix resin, volume fraction of fiber and coefficient configuration of reinforced-fiber. In consequence, these results contribute to reduce the test time and the number of tests for verification of dynamic properties under conditions of a wide strain rate range, which include creep behavior needed huge time for measurement or impact behavior with low accuracy.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) have high specific mechanical properties, so they are attractive as light-weight structure. Therefore CFRP are widely expanding application in structures of aircraft and automobile in order to reduce CO₂ emission and environmental load. Specifically, reducing weight has been important mission for automotive industries and others [1]. Some industries for mass-production need the CFRP that can be produced by high cycle process. But traditional CFRP using thermosetting resin matrix don't suit the general process because of low moldability, long curing time and low recyclability [2]. On the contrary, CFRP with thermoplastic as matrix resin has attracted attention at mass-production field, and it would be widely applied because of their excellent productivity and formability for complex shape [3,4].

By the way, polymer resin has unique time- and temperature-dependent mechanical properties called viscoelastic behavior, even if it is likely thermoplastics or thermosetting. Specially, thermoplastics exhibit strongly viscoelastic behavior than thermosetting. For this reason, if carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastics (CFRTP) are applied in some structural components under situation of changing temperature or strain rate, it will need to be concerned that the inherent mechanical properties of matrix resin will be changed accordingly with usage environments. From the point of reliability of design and of guarantee of quality, it is important to predict the characteristic variation due to changing the temperature and strain rate exactly [5-7]. On the other hand, the ratio of in-plane elastic modulus and out-of-plane shear modulus (E_1/G_{13}) is known to affect flexural modulus when E_1/G_{13} becomes large and structure becomes smaller. And since E_1/G_{13} of CFRP, especially of CFRTP, is also known to be very large compared to metallic materials, so the dependence of G_{13} on flexural modulus cannot be neglected [8]. Thus, these things considered with quantifying about both characteristic parameter (E_1 or G_{13}) and time- and temperature-dependence influencing bending behavior. It is helpful in order to analysis prediction of structural properties such as those of the automobile structure.

In this study, a theoretical model about time- and temperature- dependence of flexural elastic modulus of CFRTP was constructed by time-temperature superposition principle on viscoelastic properties inherent matrix resin. And the theoretical model was verified by dynamic three point bending test. Specially, the three point bending test was performed with the Polypropylene (PP)-based discontinuous CF mat reinforced thermoplastics (CMT) with in-plane isotropy (Figure 1) [2,9]. From these results, the influence of both in-plane modulus and out-of-plane shear modulus on bending behavior was discussed under various conditions by changing temperature and strain rate.

Fig.1 Image of CMT (a) and carbon fiber mat (b).

2 CONSTRUCTION OF THEORETICAL MODEL

2.1 Construct the flexural modulus of discontinuous CFRTP by rule of mixture.

At first, the flexural modulus of discontinuous CFRTP was constructed by based on Timoshenko beam equation. The curvature δ_b in center of rectangular beam is explained by followed equation from theory of Timoshenko.

$$\delta_b = \frac{PL^3}{48E_1I_z} + \frac{3PL}{8G_{13}A} = \frac{PL^3}{48E_1I_z} \left\{ 1 + \frac{3}{2} \left(\frac{h}{L} \right)^2 \cdot \frac{E_1}{G_{13}} \right\} \quad (1)$$

where P is the applied load, L is the span length, h is thickness of beam, A is the sectional area, I_z is second moment of area, E_1 is in-plane elastic modulus, and G_{13} is out-of-plane shear modulus. From equation (1), the relationship among flexural modulus E_b , E_1 and G_{13} is derived as follows:

$$\frac{1}{E_b} = \frac{1}{E_1} + \frac{3}{2} \left(\frac{h}{L} \right)^2 \cdot \frac{1}{G_{13}} \quad (2)$$

Thus, in the case of CFRTP beam, the flexural modulus of CFRTP E_{bc} is explained from relationships among the in-plane elastic modulus of CFRTP E_{1c} , out-of-plane shear modulus of G_{13c} and the parameter h/L as testing condition.

By the way, it is known that CFRTP has specific anisotropy that is indicated by difference between both value of tensile modulus of CFRTP E_{tc} and compressive modulus of CFRTP E_{cc} . Now the flexural modulus, the in-plane modulus, is assumed according to E_{tc} and E_{cc} by followed equation:

$$E_{1c(Theory)} = \frac{2E_{tc}}{1 + \sqrt{E_{tc}/E_{cc}}} \quad (3)$$

On the other hand, E_{1c} and G_{13c} is obtained by using the rule of mixture modified for discontinuous CFRTP. Both E_{1c} and G_{13c} is assumed as followed equations:

$$E_{1c(Mixture)} = \alpha V_f E_f + (1 - V_f) E_m \quad (4)$$

$$G_{13c(Mixture)} = \frac{\alpha \cdot G_f G_m}{V_f G_m + \alpha(1 - V_f) G_f} = \frac{G_m}{\frac{V_f}{\alpha} \cdot \frac{G_m}{G_f} + (1 - V_f)} \quad (5)$$

where V_f is volume fraction of fiber, E_f is Young's modulus of CF, E_m is Young's modulus of matrix resin, G_f is shear modulus of CF, G_m is shear modulus of matrix resin and α is shape coefficient value of carbon fiber mat. Since CF has strong anisotropy, so it should be used different value about between E_f and G_f [10]. Above both equation is modified by shape coefficient value α . In addition, G_m can be represented by using E_m from:

$$G_m = \frac{E_m}{2(1 + \nu)} \quad (6)$$

where ν is Poisson's ratio.

In this paper, α is calculated from experimental value of tensile modulus of CFRTP E_{tc} and compressive modulus of CFRTP E_{cc} by using equation (3) and (4). α is presumed by

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{if } E_{1c(Theory)} = E_{1c(Mixture)} \\ \alpha &= \frac{2E_{tc} - (1 + \sqrt{E_{tc}/E_{cc}})(1 - V_f)E_m}{V_f E_f (1 + \sqrt{E_{tc}/E_{cc}})} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

As these equation (4), (5), (6) and (2) lead the equation (8) :

$$\frac{1}{E_{bc}} = \frac{1}{\alpha \cdot V_f E_f + (1 - V_f) \cdot E_m} + \frac{3}{2} \left(\frac{h}{L} \right)^2 \cdot \frac{V_f E_m + 2\alpha G_f (1 - V_f)(1 + \nu)}{\alpha G_f E_m} \quad (8)$$

As a result of Equation (8), the flexural modulus is constructed by constituent material properties. In the other words, Equation (8) suggest that flexural modulus E_{bc} , based on E_{1c} and G_{13c} , shows viscoelasticity behavior due to matrix resin properties.

2.2 Derivation about viscoelastic properties of matrix resin.

It is widely known that polymer resin has viscoelastic properties which is influenced by time (strain rate: $\dot{\epsilon}$) and temperature T . The viscoelastic properties are obtained as storage modulus E_m' which has temperature dependence by dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) as followed equation (9):

$$\begin{aligned} E_m' &= E_m \cdot \frac{\omega^2 \tau^2}{1 + \omega^2 \tau^2} \\ \text{※ } \tan \delta &= \frac{1}{\omega \tau} \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

where ω is frequency, which means strain rate, and τ is relaxation time. Now $\omega \tau$, time parameter, can be represented by loss tangent $\tan \delta$. Thus, Young's modulus of matrix resin $E_{m(DMA)}$ which has viscoelastic modulus, is derived followed equation from equation (9):

$$E_{m(DMA)} = E_m = E_m' \cdot \{(\tan \delta)^2 + 1\} \quad (10)$$

According to equation (10), the time- and temperature-dependence of matrix resin was explain by E_m' and $\tan \delta$. The shear modulus G_m is calculated by the time- and temperature-dependency with equation (6) and (10), and both E_m and G_m were expanded themselves relational expression of time- and temperature-dependence. Thus, the time- and temperature dependence of G_m is defined by

$$G_{m(DMA)} = \frac{E_{m(DMA)}}{2(1 + \nu)} \quad (11)$$

These equation indicated that the time- and temperature- dependent Young's modulus of matrix resin can be predicted by the result of DMA. For a result, if viscoelasticity of matrix resin is obtained, E_{1c} and G_{13c} are presumed with quantitatively.

2.3 Constructing the theoretical model of E_{bc} reflected the time- and temperature-dependent.

The theoretical model of flexural modulus reflecting the time- and temperature-dependent $E_{bc(\dot{\varepsilon}, T)}$ is constructed by substituting the above equations for Timoshenko theory. $E_{bc(\dot{\varepsilon}, T)}$ is defined by:

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{E_{bc(\dot{\varepsilon}, T)}} \\ &= \frac{1}{\alpha \cdot V_f E_f + (1 - V_f) \cdot (E_{m(DMA)})} + \frac{3}{2} \left(\frac{h}{L} \right)^2 \frac{V_f (E_{m(DMA)}) + 2\alpha G_f (1 - V_f)(1 + \nu)}{\alpha G_f (E_{m(DMA)})} \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

Equation (12) indicate that the time- and temperature dependent flexural modulus of discontinuous CFRTP can be explained by assumed both matrix resin viscoelastic properties and accurate shape factor of CF mat. In consequence, the theoretical model about flexural modulus of discontinuous CFRTP E_{bc} which is reflected the time- and temperature-dependence of both in-plane modulus flexural E_1 and out-of-shear modulus G_{13c} was constructed.

3 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

3.1 Preparation of specimen

Dynamic three point bending test was conducted using CMT in order to measure the flexural modulus of discontinuous CFRTP. And the viscoelastic modulus of matrix resin was measured using resin coupon by DMA. The detail of these test procedure are discuss later.

CMT sheet was composed from CF mat made from discontinuous CF and PP as the matrix resin. CF mat was made by TORAY industries, Inc. with T700 (tensile modulus 230 GPa; tensile strength; 4900 MPa). CF length can be designed and CF dispersion is isotropic in-plane. On the other hand, PP matrix was made from homo PP, and acid-modified PP and obtained by using a twin-screw extruder in melting-mixed. The content of homo PP and acid-modified PP was changed in order to control various IFSS. CMT were obtained by melt-pressing 200 g/m² of the CF mat and PP films. CF mats and PP films were laid up against each other and PP films were melt-pressured at 220 degree Celsius for 2 min under 4 MPa of pressure. The sheet was cooled under the same pressure until the material temperature reached 50 degree Celsius, the CFRP sheet was obtained. V_f was controlled by number of PP films.

Matrix resin coupon which is made from same PP constituting CMT was prepared for measuring storage modulus. The dimension of the test specimen were length of 46 mm, width of 6.4 mm and thickness of 1.6 mm.

3.2 Evaluation the tensile modulus of CMT

The tensile modulus of CMT were evaluated at 25 degree Celsius using the ASTM D3039 at a crosshead speed 1.0%/mm at center of specimen. The shape of specimen was rectangle with gage length of 150 mm, width of 25 mm and thickness of 2 mm. And the tensile modulus was evaluated at liner region on stress-strain curve.

3.3 Evaluation the compressive modulus of CMT

The compressive modulus of CMT were evaluated at 25 degree Celsius to refer to the ASTM D3410 at a crosshead speed 0.5%/mm at center of specimen. The shape of specimen was rectangle with gage length of 10 mm, width of 20 mm, thickness of 2 mm, and tab length of 50 mm. At the part of grip, tab which is made from same of specimen was attached by adhesion. The compression strain was measured by strain gage at center of specimen in order to evaluate the compressive modulus. And the compressive modulus was evaluated at liner region on stress-strain curve.

3.4 Dynamic viscoelasticity of matrix PP

The temperature dependence of the viscoelastic properties (storage modulus: E_m' , loss tangent: $\tan\delta$) of matrix PP was evaluated by dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) in dual cantilever bending mode at various dynamic frequency and the amplitude 0.01% using a viscoelastometer instrument (TA instruments, RSA-III). And the specimens were tested over a range from -30 degree Celsius to 150 degree Celsius with interval of 5 degree Celsius. And the equation of calculating the average strain rate from frequency was defined by

$$\bar{\epsilon} = \frac{4a}{100T} \quad (13)$$

where a is amplitude of strain and T is period.

3.5 Evaluation the dynamic flexural modulus of CMT by dynamic three point bending test

The three point bending test was performed in order to verify the theoretical model of E_{bc} under various strain rates and temperatures. In this study, flexural modulus of CMT was measured to refer to JIS K 7084 and testing condition shown Table 1. The dimensions of specimens were 40 mm of span length, 50 mm of width and 2 mm of thickness. Since the purpose of experiment was to obtain the flexural modulus, so the experimental value were recorded until 1.5 % strain. And flexural modulus was evaluated at liner region on stress-strain curve.

4 RESULT AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Viscoelasticity of the matrix resin PP

The time- and temperature-dependence of the viscoelastic properties (Young's modulus E_m) of the PP by using the equations (10) and (13) was shown as Figure 2. A x-axis indicates the strain rate and y-axis indicates the Young's modulus. And the individual line means the result of different measurement temperature. The Young's modulus shows clear strain rate dependency at each measurement temperature. However, transition of the Young's modulus by strain rate dependency was larger at higher temperature than at lower temperature. In other words, this results suggested that the sensitivity of the Young's modulus E_m to strain rate dependency was changed by varying the temperature.

Fig.2 Strain rate dependence of dynamic viscoelastic properties of PP.

4.2 Evaluation of the coefficient value α from tensile and compressive modulus

The tensile and compressive modulus of CMT were evaluated in order to estimate the coefficient value α by using equation (7), as shown in Table 1. Now the value of E_m in the equation (7) applied the experimental value from DMA at strain rate of $4.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$, which is the same level with strain rate at static test. As a result, E_{tc} and E_{cc} were not so different and the $E_{tc(\text{Theory})}$ was intermediate value of E_{tc} and E_{cc} . As the result, the value of α was about 0.3. This result suggests that the utilization of CF reinforced effect for E_{tc} was 30% of V_f . It is a reasonable result for the quite isotropic random CF-mat of controlled CF length and CF dispersion. After this section, value of α is established as constant value.

Table 1 Reference of each modulus and shape coefficient value α .

Temp [°C]	E_{tc} [GPa]	E_{cc} [GPa]	$E_{tc(\text{Theory})}$ [GPa]	shape coefficient value α [-]
25	14.7	15.2	14.8	0.279

4.3 Dynamic flexural modulus of CMT

The strain dependency of flexural modulus of CMT $E_{bc(\text{Experiment})}$ was evaluated by dynamic three point bending test at various temperatures and strains rate. Figure 3 shows stress-strain curves which was conducted test with various strain rate at 25 degree Celsius. The flexural modulus $E_{bc(\text{Experiment})}$ was calculated from slope at liner region. It suggests that $E_{bc(\text{Experiment})}$ increase with increasing the strain rate. Certainly, these experimental results clarified that the flexural modulus of CMT $E_{bc(\text{Experiment})}$ has strain rate dependence at room temperature.

Next, the dynamic bending test with several strain rates were conducted at various temperature. Figure 4 shows the example of several results of bending tests. These results also indicate that $E_{bc(\text{Experiment})}$ increase with increasing the strain rate. However, these results show that transition of $E_{bc(\text{Experiment})}$ was exactly large at higher temperature comparing with lower temperature condition.

This result indicated similar to characteristic of just a PP. As a result, it is assumed that time- and temperature-dependency of $E_{bc(Experiment)}$ strongly reflects the viscoelastic properties of PP.

Fig.3 Stress-strain curve of three-point bending test on various strain rate.

Fig.4 Stress-strain curve of three-point bending test on various strain rate at -30 degree Celsius (a) and 100 degree Celsius (b).

4.4 Verifying the theoretical model

Figure 5 shows the relationships between flexural modulus of CMT E_{bc} and strain rate at various temperatures. And there are two kinds of E_{bc} which are experimental value of dynamic bending test $E_{bc(Experiment)}$ and theoretical value calculated from equation (12) $E_{bc(\xi,T)}$. Now, $E_{1c(Mixture)}$ and

$G_{13c(Mixture)}$ were calculated by using the equations (4), (5), (10) and (11). In this case, the E_m applied the results of DMA.

They are certainly similar value and tendency for change among temperature and strain rate. Additionally, it is obvious that transition of E_{bc} by changing temperature was bigger than it by changing strain rate. From these results, the theoretical value $E_{bc(\varepsilon,T)}$ agree with experimental value $E_{bc(Experiment)}$ obviously. On the other words, accuracy of theoretical model and presumed parameter were supported by dynamic three point bending test.

Fig.5 Comparison of $E_{bc(Experiment)}$ and $E_{bc(Theory)}$ on various strain-rate

4.5 Evaluation of $E_{1c(Mixture)}$ and $G_{13c(Mixture)}$

Before this section, validity of the accurate theoretical model was substantiated by experiment. In this section, $E_{1c(Mixture)}$ and $G_{13c(Mixture)}$ were quantify from our theoretical model. Figure 6 shows the relationship between E_{1c} , G_{13c} and strain rate at 25 degree Celsius. They are increasing with increasing the strain rate. In specially, G_{13c} was relatively smaller than E_{1c} . But the strain rate dependence of G_{13c} was stronger than the strain rate dependence of E_{1c} . This results suggest that the contribution of matrix resin properties is different for E_{1c} and G_{13c} . The reason was assumed that E_{1c} obtain the sufficient utilization of CF reinforced effect. On the other hand, G_{13c} indicated particularly the strain rate dependency. Because it is known that CF was weak to shear load. G_{13c} was relatively reflected the stronger matrix resin properties.

Fig.6 Comparison time dependence of Young's modulus (a) and out-of-plane shear modulus (b) at some strain rate.

5 CONCLUSION

In this study, the theoretical model about time- and temperature-dependent flexural modulus of discontinuous CFRTP ($E_{bc}(\dot{\epsilon}, T)$) was constructed and verified by experiments. For a result, time- and temperature-dependent $E_{bc(Experimental)}$ was able to be predicted easily by constructed model (equation (12)). Additionally, theoretical model, that is equation (12), was verified by conducting the quite accurate experiment. And following conclusions were obtained.

1. About the flexural modulus of CMT, the theoretical model about time- and temperature-dependence was constructed by installing the temperature-dependent viscoelastic properties of matrix resin based on the theory of Timoshenko.
2. A validity of the accurate theoretical model was supported by considering the influence of both constituent material parameter (PP and shape of CF mat) and out-of-shear modulus G_{13c} .
3. The theoretical model was verified by conducting the three point bending test under the condition controlled both strain rate and temperature precisely.
4. The strain rate dependence of G_{13c} was stronger than the strain rate dependence of E_{1c} . In specially, G_{13c} was smaller than E_{1c} .

These results are important information for CFRTP, which E_1/G_{13} is known to be very large. It will be expected that the predictability about bending behavior of structural parts is improved for the practical design like automobile parts. Especially, the decrease of flexural modulus was predicted in the case of higher temperature and low strain rate according to our theoretical model. Thus, this knowledge will be helpful to consider properties such as bending creep behavior which needs quite long time to measure the properties.

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REFERENCES

- [1] J. Takahashi and T. Ishikawa: *Proceedings of ITHEC 2014* (2014), 30-31.
- [2] N. Hirano, H. Muramatsu and T. Inoue, *Advanced Composite Material*, 23, 2, 2014, 151-161.
- [3] J. Takahashi and T. Ishikawa, *Proceedings of SAMPE SEICO14*, 2014, 181-188.
- [4] Vaidya UK, Chawla KK. *Processing of Fiber Reinforced Thermoplastic Composite. Int. Mater. Rev.* 2008;53:185-218
- [5] Venkata S. Chevali, Derrick R. Dean and Gregg M. Janowski: *Composites: Part A*, 40, 2009, 870-877.
- [6] Venkata S. Chevali and Gregg M. Janowski: *Composites: Part A*, 41, 2010, 1253-1262.
- [7] Y. Miyano and M. Nakada : *Experimental Mechanics*, 46, 2006, 155-162.
- [8] D.F.Adams, L.A.Carlsson and R.B.Pipes: *Experimental Characterization of Advanced Composite Materials* (3rd Ed.), CRC Press (2002)
- [9] M. Honma, A. Tsuchiya, N. Hirano and T. Hashimoto, “Novel carbon-fiber reinforced stampable thermoplastic sheet with high strength”, *Proceedings of the 18th International Conference on Composite Materials*, 2011
- [10] P.Morgan: *Carbon Fiber and their Composites*, (2005), 935-949.